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DESIGNING AS DEMONSTRATION: JUSTIFYING INDUSTRIAL DESIGN PROJECTS WITHIN PHD RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT

PhD research that integrates modes of design practice has gained popularity and greater acceptance in the art and design sector in recent years. Correspondingly, a body of literature and debate has developed around its purpose, distinctiveness, legitimacy and qualities. Disagreement still abounds on many fronts including the use and meaning of certain terminology, distinctiveness of design research practice compared to other fields of research and other forms of design practice; as well as debate on appropriate modes of design practice methods, quality and rigor. In the meantime an increasing number of completed Design PhDs offer researchers examples of how design practice can be mobilised in Doctoral research. This paper discusses a recently completed PhD in context to distinctiveness and a particular mode of design research practice - 'design as demonstration'. The example PhD investigates the role and potential of Industrial Design to confront product obsolescence in consumer electronics sectors. The adopted research methodology contains design projects that demonstrate practical application of new theory.

Keywords: Design Research, PhD Design Practices, Product Obsolescence.

INTRODUCTION

PhD research that integrates design practice is now well established in many higher education institutions, but remains poorly defined.

A useful generalised definition of design research practices is that it produces *prototypes*, *products* and *models* as a means of framing and understanding particular problems and describing proposed outcomes or a preferred state (Zimmerman & Forlizzi 2008).

However, as a relatively new field it needs to be more specific, to design researchers and others, as to 'what it is' and 'why it is different' from other fields of research and other forms of design practice? Often the first stumbling point is clarity in the use of terms such as 'practice-led research', 'practice-based research' and 'research through design'.

Despite common usage many declare such terms as vague and prone to ambiguity (Sevaldson 2010, Niedderer & Stokes 2007, Durling & Niedderer 2007, Pedgley & Wormald 2007 Langrish 2000).

"Precisely because there is no need for adherence to a single definition, we are obliged to make our usage clear. This does more than help others to understand terms as we use them. It also helps to ensure that we understand what we are saying" (Friedman 2002: 389). Defining the relationship between design research and other academic disciplines (Margolin 2010) is also called for.

While for others, the distinctiveness of design practice within a PhD, as opposed to 'stand-alone' design practice, is important (Langrish 2000; Durling & Niedderer 2007). These discussions remain active, but mostly unresolved within different sections of the art and design community. For the PhD design researcher this can be confusing on how to locate, frame and justify their design practice within a doctoral research setting. However, there exists a growing number of awarded PhDs that incorporate design practice that can offer instructive examples

to others (Pedgley & Wormald 2007; Neidderer 2004; Rust et. al, 1999).

This paper contributes to the field by offering an example of a recently completed PhD that integrates Industrial Design practice (Park 2009). It illustrates how design practice can be framed within a research perspective and categorised as a mode of design practice in PhD research.

The PhD research sits within the emerging field of sustainable design - yet another vaguely applied and often poorly understood field (Chick & Micklethwaite 2011). It investigates the role and potential of Industrial Design to confront product obsolescence in consumer electronics sectors. The research (discussed latter in this paper) seeks to understand how the design can prolong product lifespans by learning from existing examples, which result in prolonged product lifespans, and applying those principles or strategies to design projects? The adopted research methodology contains design projects that are best described as 'design as demonstration' (Durling & Niedderer 2007). These include three of the author's own design projects in demonstrating and illustrating the theories investigated within the research.

DISTINCTIVENESS

For PhD study the candidate must demonstrate an understanding of the practice of research (Durling & Niedderer 2007). A PhD is not awarded for design practice alone. This is not to say that design practice is inconsequential or inappropriate, but that the PhD candidate who incorporates design practice needs to know what it contributes to the PhD and why it is valuable over other research methods. Pedgley & Wormald (2007) pose the question; "What would be lost without the designing?" In terms of rigor, what is the research function of the design project(s)? Are they an appropriate method in response to research questions or should other methods be employed? "Rigor in research is the strength of the chain of reasoning" (Biggs & Büchler 2007: 69). Without it, "then there will be no difference in evidence between that which is absent and that which is present, but merely has not been found" (Biggs & Büchler 2007: 66). The researcher needs to be rigorous in defending the purpose and reasoning for design projects.

As a new field, design research needs to position itself in relation to other fields of research and know what theory and practices it shares and its points of difference. This can be done at various levels, from the theoretical to the applied, starting with research perspective, comparison to other research fields, and/or through specific research methodologies, methods and processes that have particular design research practice attributes.

RESEARCH PERSPECTIVE

Established discipline fields often adhere to a clearly defined research perspective (Guba & Lincoln cited in Mont 2004). For example, the traditions of science are grounded in a positivist epistemology that claims to be 'objective' in its understanding of the observed world. On the other hand, other academic fields such as the humanities and social sciences often find such perspectives inadequate in enabling a coherent understanding of the world. They are more likely to adopt an interpretive model based upon a constructive or subjective epistemology.

So where does design fit? Does it slot somewhere between a positivist epistemology and that of constructed and conjectural meaning, or does design belong elsewhere on its own (Vaishnavi & Kuechler 2009), or in multiple perspectives as such clear-cut distinctions are often over emphasised (Sevaldson 2010)? Irrespective, of what ontological and epistemology perspective is implied within a design researchers' 'world view' their philosophical position should be clear. Indeed, for the very title for the award 'Doctor in Philosophy' it implies that the researcher is engaged with the philosophical contexts of their research endeavour.

Design, both as a professional discipline and a field of research, can be considered as a horizontal activity that cuts across vertical silos of specialist disciplines (Chick & Micklethwaite 2011). Freidman also offers a complementary model of fields or domains represented by six wedges making a circle that is bisected by a horizon of theoretical study to one side and fields of practice and application on the other. "Moving clockwise from the left-most triangle, these domains are (1) natural sciences, (2) humanities and liberal arts, (3) social and behavioural sciences, (4) human professions and services, (5) creative and applied arts, and (6)

technology and engineering. Design may involve any or all of these domains, in differing aspect and proportion depending on the nature of the project at hand or the problem to be solved.”

(Freidman 2002: 6)

Yet another means of making the distinction between design and other disciplines is that design is ‘Synthetic’ - a process of synthesis that is oriented toward inventing and designing (be it an artefact, system or service). While other specialist disciplines, for example, mathematics, chemistry and physics are typically ‘Analytical’ - in that they are about discovering specific knowledge (Owen 1998) “Unlike scientists who describe how the world is, designers suggest how it might be” (Lawson 1997: 112). Traditional science ‘takes things apart’ while design ‘puts things together’ through a process of syntheses and allowing a “creative reasoning” (Whiteley 2000: 23). Design activities such as sketching and modelling can enable a problem to be understood. Designers can make a unique contribution to research by creating things that allow other people to see the world differently (Rust, et al. 1999). Thus design can be conceived as a synthesising process of analytical knowledge. The example PhD reported upon in this paper sits within the emerging field of sustainable design. A field that is often defined as requiring a multi-disciplinary and multi-mode research perspective to accommodate a diverse range of social, environmental and economic dynamics that often shape the research context. Such an approach can accommodate the objectiveness of scientific positivism to the conjectural subjectivism where the findings are transactional and mediated interpretations. However, it has been argued that it is the positivism of scientific reductionism that has shaped our society since the Industrial Revolution and has led us to the current crisis of sustainability (Margolin 1998). Isolated specialist knowledge and scientific reductionism are claimed to be inadequate to deal with the complex interrelationships between society, the environment and the economy (Capra 2002). Design’s qualities as a horizontal activity that synthesises knowledge across disciplines offers great potential in such a setting.

Thus this example PhD embraces a more accommodating research perspective. It adopts a

multi-mode approach that is more aligned to a constructivist research perspective. Crotty (1998) defines constructivism as, “all knowledge, and therefore all meaningful reality as, is contingent upon human practices, being constructed in and out of interaction between human beings and their world, and developed and transmitted within an essentially social context”.

With the inclusion of the author’s own design projects within the research, the author becomes ‘involved’ in what is being studied. A positivist approach would require different research methods in which the researcher aims to exert no influence or bias on what is being studied. This objectivity is well understood in fields such as the sciences, but may not be appropriate in a design research setting.

DESIGN PRACTICE

Additional to understanding design research in regard to other fields of research there is a need to understand the distinctiveness of design practice within PhD research over other typical design practices.

There are broadly two modes of designing within a research context. One mode is to observe others designing, while the other mode of research is based upon one’s own designing (Durling & Niedderer 2007). The distinction here is between third person as ‘observer’ and first person as the ‘designer’. In addition a further distinction of second person can also be added (Sevaldson 2010). This is where research is collaborative, such as within an action research methodology that could include participatory, co-design or collaborative design methods.

Design projects undertaken within this PhD follow a design process as typically encountered in Industrial Design practice. However, the context of the projects contains specific qualities that make it distinct from other design practices. For design practice to qualify as PhD research, it should satisfy a specific range of criteria or qualities (Rust 2002; Langrish 2000; Durling & Niedderer 2007; Pedgley & Wormald 2007). A principle feature of PhD design practice that differs from other forms of research in professional practice is that it is a systematic enquiry (Archer 1981) “that is reported in a form which allows the research methods and outcomes to be

PhD Design Practice	Typical Design Practice
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematic investigations and enquiry into ... • Asks and responds to questions • Selects appropriate methods, systematic • Evidenced based • Transparent and Documented • Analysis and Discovery • Generates new theories, original • Takes risks • Tells others what to do • Findings are public, an enduring record • Locatable and searchable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application of professional skills in designing • Ad hoc to systematic • Tacit knowing • Learning through experience • Intuitive decision-making • Can be routine • Can push boundaries • Often is information gathering

Table 1. Qualities of PhD design research practices over typical design practice (Adapted from Cross cited in Pedgley & Wormald 2007: 75)

accessible to others” (Allison et al. 1996: 21 cited in Pedgley et al. 2007). The table below is an adapted list of qualities that distinguishes PhD design research practices from other typical design practices. [Table 1]

DESIGNING AS DEMONSTRATION

First person design projects undertaken within this example PhD are best described by Durling & Niedderer’s five-part model as “designing as demonstration” (2007). Their investigative designing model includes: designing to test, designing quick and dirty, designing as demonstration, designing as ideal, and designing as creative exploration. They describe ‘designing as demonstration’ as resulting in a concept design or specification. Design skills can be utilised, “to provide a vision of how such a specification might be instantiated, and provides one example of such a design that might yet be subjected to rigorous further examination”. The thesis’ argument is not reliant upon the artefact, “it follows that the PhD would not be awarded for the conceptualisation or production of the artefact, but would be awarded for the evidence of process that led to the production of the specification” (Durling & Niedderer 2007: 12).

Design projects offer a means of demonstrating theory and developing new knowledge. In this particular PhD the research aim was to identify and develop understanding of strategies that can prolong the lifespans of products and thereby apply such

principles or strategies to structured design projects (Park 2009). Three strategies Piggybacking, Reassignment and Scripting were identified and defined to address the most significant form of ‘relative’ obsolescence in consumer electronic product sectors. Obsolescence of consumer electronic occurs mostly because of ‘relative’ rather than ‘absolute’ factors (Cooper 2010). Relative obsolescence mainly includes: technological change, psychological factors, cultural practices and economic circumstances (cost of repair or replacement). While absolute obsolescence refers to aspects of functional failure of a product. Prior to the main design activity noted above, the first part of the PhD research commenced with a review of existing examples of long product lifespans through well-established modes of research enquiry such as the literature review, curated examples and observational methods. The literature review revealed historical, cultural and artefact examples, as well as offering a theoretical framework in which to understand the sociological, psychological and economic dimensions of consumption and product obsolescence. Observational and curated examples of longer lifespan products were enhanced through a structured seminar activity involving approximately 20 participants. A four-week pilot design project followed with another group of participants to trial selected design strategies. The pilot project enabled adjustments and refinements to the strategies to be applied to the third and most significant design

activity undertaken as a part of this PhD research. This first phase of the design research was undertaken in a second person perspective - as the researcher in immersed as both the leader and observer of the activity.

If phase one of the PhD research could be summarised as analysis, phase two is the synthesis phase of the research through demonstration design projects. The main undertaking during this phase of the PhD was the task of applying selected product lifespan strategies to demonstration design projects in response to research questions;

- Can specific examples of prolonged product lifespans be described and structured into formalised strategies?
- Can product lifespan strategies be successfully applied to design projects?

The designing as demonstration projects are a means in which to understand the application of specific theorised strategies. Designing as demonstration outcomes “would not be an 'ideal' product, or the only possible manifestation of the specification, but would have the sole purpose of demonstrating that

Figure 1. DABlife Piggybacked DAB module, the piggybacking module receives digital audio broadcasts through the existing radio's aerial and then rebroadcasts it as a FM signal back to the same radio.

the specification could have practical outcomes” (Durling & Niedderer 2007: 12). The following example illustrates one particular designing as demonstration project. It involves the application of an identified strategy of ‘Piggybacking’ applied to a design project. [Figure 1]

EXAMPLE DESIGN PROJECT: PIGGYBACKING

Piggybacking as a strategy can be described as enabling renewed and enhanced functionality in a technologically obsolete product through the addition of 'add-on' or secondary devices. The strategy was applied to the design of a digital audio receiver that works in conjunction with existing (potentially obsolete) AM/FM radios. It enables an existing radio to receive both Digital Audio Broadcasting (DAB) and Wi-Fi Internet radio services by attaching (Piggybacking) a secondary module onto the aerial of the existing radio.

Titled DABlife, the piggybacking module receives digital audio broadcast signals via the existing radio's aerial and then rebroadcasts the signals back as FM signals to the same radio. The design features a removable remote control panel that reveals a backlit display. Other radios within a vicinity of a 30 metres radius can also be tuned into the same FM frequency to receive the digital or Internet radio broadcast. DABlife demonstrates how a piggybacking strategy can slow technological obsolescence by extending the functionality of existing radio equipment; enabling potentially obsolete equipment to traverse the technological step change of the digital broadcasting switchover. [Figure 1]

DESIGN METHOD

The project was documented in detail using a staged design process as typically encountered in many expressions of Industrial Design practice. In this instance, the design process practice is discussed and documented in the PhD thesis at each stage: Design brief, Concept exploration, Design development, Design documentation and Evaluation.

Once the design brief was finalised, concepts drawings and 3D mock-ups were developed. The design of household radios varies enormously presenting significant technical challenges for a

Figure 2. Proof of concept 'bread board' test rig

Piggybacking approach. Concept designs focused upon exploring the possibilities of one design configuration that would suit the widest range of radios. In parallel, a 'bread board' test rig was devised to test the FM modulation of a DAB signal through the existing radios aerial. [Figure 2 & 3] From the field of possible concept designs, a

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of DAB-FM modulation

preferred design was selected, against the criteria established in the brief for further design development. Innovative features of the design include direct aerial attachment of the module and a

Figure 4. Preferred concept sketch

docking remote control that nests back onto the fascia of the main module when not in use. [Figure 4]

2D General Assembly (GA) drawings were produced to resolve the internal configuration and arrangement of components, housing construction, form detailing and finish specification. From the GA drawing an appearance model was made and photographed for evaluation and documentation purposes.

Evaluation of the project was framed exclusively in response to the research questions on how well the final design conveyed the concept of the piggybacking strategy and that the design strategy could have practical outcomes. No technical, usability or perceptual testing or evaluation of the actual produced design was undertaken. The design artefact was not evaluated as to its likely success or otherwise or as an optimum or improved solution. Its purpose is to demonstrate, through a design project, the application of the piggybacking strategy. [Figure 5]

CONCLUSION

This paper offers an example of design practice in PhD research. It does so as a means to discuss qualities of design research in regard to research perspective, other fields of research and modes of design practice. The presented project offers an example of one mode of designing in PhD research - designing as demonstration. If design research makes claims to its distinctiveness from other fields of research and other design practices it needs to articulate why and what qualities and purpose it offers. As a relatively new field PhD design researchers need to consider their research perspective, methodological framework and why their chosen approach is appropriate compared to other research methods.

Equally, the PhD researcher needs to know that their design practice methods are rigorous in reporting their methodological chain of reasoning linking back to the research aims and research questions. Design practice in PhD research can bring new, unique and rewarding insights to research problems. However, to do so it needs to know what it brings to the research and why it is justified. A PhD is not awarded for design practice alone.

Figure 5. Sequence of form studies and final appearance model of DAB 'Piggybacking' Module

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